

Aerodynamics of Large Aspect Ratio Wings with Distributed Propellers via The Vortex-Lattice Method and High-Fidelity Simulations

Zachary Ciera*, Bryn Jones†, Peter Nagy‡, Marco Fossati§
University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, G1 1XJ, United Kingdom

This work presents a study of the aerodynamics of strut-braced Large Aspect Ratio Wings with Distributed Hybrid-Electric Propulsion. It is intended to assess and quantify the ability of lower-fidelity methods such as the Vortex-Lattice Method with actuator discs to address the aerodynamic interaction of non-conventional aircraft configurations. The use of the Vortex-Lattice Method is crucial in the context of multi-disciplinary design and optimisation where many different geometrical configurations and their associated aerodynamic performance needs to be considered in a cost-effective manner. The predictions resulting from the low-fidelity study are compared to the corresponding high-fidelity solutions with actuator disk. Discrepancies between the two approaches are addressed in terms of the flow physics of the air moving around the air frame and propellers.

I. Nomenclature

A	=	Area	C_{D0}	=	Drag coefficient at 0° AoA
AoA	=	Angle of Attack	$\alpha C_{D,Min}$	=	AoA of Minimum drag
α_0	=	Zero lift Angle of Attack	$C_{D,Min}$	=	Minimum drag coefficient
C_D	=	Drag coefficient	$\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha}$	=	Lift curve gradient
C_L	=	Lift coefficient	t/c	=	Thickness to chord ratio
C_{L0}	=	Lift coefficient at 0° AoA			

II. Introduction and Motivation

OVER the course of several decades, the demand for sustainable and environmentally friendly solutions to civilian aviation has consistently increased. This demand has been primarily through an increase in public awareness; driving financial incentives towards investment into such technologies. As a result, a variety of in-depth conceptual studies have been conducted to try and meet this increasing demand. The relevant study for this case has been the Subsonic Ultra Green Aircraft Research (SUGAR), headed by NASA. Phase 1 of this study was able to identify Large Aspect Ratio Wings (LARW) as a viable avenue to explore [1], with further work in Phase 2 building upon this result as part of a more focused investigation.

Phase 2 of the project was able to support the findings of Phase 1 whilst also suggesting that the investigation of Distributed Hybrid Electric Propulsion (DHEP) would be highly advantageous [2]. The findings from SUGAR have been supported by a range of further studies that investigate LARWs and DHEP [3–7]. The results of which show that the advantages of this conceptual aircraft configuration are not just seen during cruise, but also through low-speed applications. Furthermore, the advantages of hybrid electric propulsion are a worthwhile area of study from the perspective of near airport operations, with switching from SAF and fully electric modes being used to reduce the impact on local communities near to airports. In the broader scheme of things these new aircraft configurations have the potential to allow for shorter runways for take-off and landing, utilising steeper climb/descent flight paths.

*PhD Student, Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, 75 Montrose St, Glasgow G1 1XJ, AIAA Student Member

†Post-doctoral researcher, Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, 75 Montrose St, Glasgow G1 1XJ

‡PhD Student, Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, 75 Montrose St, Glasgow G1 1XJ, AIAA Student Member

§Professor, Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, 75 Montrose St, Glasgow G1 1XJ, AIAA Member

To investigate these concepts further, there are two investigation pathways that are available to researchers: physical prototypes and computational simulations. The physical model approach will be undeniably the most accurate approach, with concepts already in development such as what is being explored with the X-66, developed in collaboration with NASA and Boeing. However, the development of such demonstrators is highly limited from a design perspective, with the building and development of requires both a high financial and time investment. The alternative approach is to use Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) to analyse a range of configurations. This approach presents a far more accessible option for most researchers, allowing for appropriate analysis of potential designs without the need for physical models.

However, CFD simulations do not offer a perfect solution. There is a significant trade-off between the accuracy of simulations and the viability of running said simulations. The option of RANS, LES, or DNS will give moderate to highly detailed information of the expected performance of an aircraft. Therefore, researchers may decide to explore lower fidelity methods such as using Vortex Panel and Vortex-Lattice Method (VLM) approaches. VLM offers a potentially fast and computationally cheap method to complete design studies, such as an optimisation study. However, it is uncertain just how accurate these methods are in comparison to high fidelity approaches.

Therefore, it is important to comparatively understand the limitations and benefits of the the methods in order to make a reasonable decision about which to use. The goals of this study are:

- 1) Completion of a comparative analysis between RANS and VLM simulations for a given configuration under a set flight environment to determine the presence of significant inaccuracies.
- 2) Identification of the specific cause of the inaccuracies by inspecting key features of the flow.
- 3) Variation of the configuration, informed by the results of simulations. Attempting to minimise the presence of potential effecting flow features, completing another comparative analysis.

With the completion of these goals, it is possible to gain greater insight to the cause of inaccuracies; the impact of specific flow features/physics on the accuracy of the result from VLM approaches; and attempt to inform the use of VLM as a tool for aircraft design.

III. Methodology

For this process to be effective a rigorous methodology must first be defined. For the two methods to be properly compared, we shall focus on the lift and drag coefficients that are predicted for a set aircraft configuration across a series of flight angles. From these lift and drag coefficients, corresponding lift and drag curves will be generated that aim to predict key variables that may be targeted as part of a potential optimisation study. This will require definition of an appropriate sample aircraft geometry along with proper definitions of the relevant propeller configurations. Furthermore, an appropriate environmental definition must also be created. Regarding the geometry of the aircraft, there has already been extensive research aimed at defining an appropriate design space. Using this the following parameters were chosen.

Aircraft Geometry							
Aspect Ratio	Taper Ratio	Root Twist	Relative Tip Twist	Strut Twist	Strut Chord	t/c Root	t/c Tip
20	0.32	0°	-2°	0°	1.2515 m	0.15	0.115

Table 1 Baseline Simulation Aircraft Geometry

This represents a reasonable configuration of a conceptual LARW with DHEP. The aircraft uses the Airbus A320 wing area of $122.4 m^2$ as a further constraining factor. Along with this there are two defined aerofoils one for the strut and one for the wing. The strut uses a standard NACA 0024 aerofoil, whilst the wing uses a GA (W)-2. The resulting aircraft is illustrated below:

Fig. 1 Clean Configuration

The environmental conditions are chosen to properly represent the conditions that the aircraft is likely to encounter. In this case a flight altitude of 8000m is assumed. Regarding the choice of Mach number, for the high-speed cruise environment the aircraft is limited due to the propellers to lower speeds than a traditional jet airliner. As such the flight Mach number will be limited to 0.6. Finally, to simplify the analysis of the aircraft the angles of attack will be limited to between -5° and 5° to ensure that the lift curve remains linear, avoiding stall regions.

High-Speed Cruise					
Altitude	Pressure	Temperature	Air Density	Mach Number	AoA Range
8000 m	35600 Pa	236.15 K	0.5253 kg/m ³	0.6	$[-5^\circ:5^\circ]$

Table 2 Flight Environment

Finally, the propellers need to be defined. This is done by first setting a target thrust over the wing. A chosen thrust of 20kN was used, this was deemed to be a feasible value to properly counteract the drag from flight. Like the flight conditions the tip Mach number of the propellers must be limited to below Mach 1, in this case a value of 0.67 was chosen. Regarding the actual propeller sizing an inboard and outboard propeller was defined, a total of four propellers were used to as a sample DHEP configuration. The thrust over the wing will be split between the inboard and outboard propellers. With the chosen configuration the inboard will be generating far more thrust proportionally than the outboard, the splitting has been defined by a ratio between the thrust of the inboard to the sum of the thrust generated by the outboard propellers. This process allows the propellers to be fully defined as follows:

Propeller Parameters				
Thrust Over Wing	Inboard Diameter	Outboard Diameter	Number of Disks	$T_{\text{Inboard}} / (\sum T_{\text{Outboard}})$
20 kN	4.687 m	3.649 m	4	0.55

Table 3 Propeller Parameters

With all these parameters defined the full aircraft is shown below:

Fig. 2 Full Configuration

With the RANS simulations an actuator disc model can be used to approximate the effect of propellers. Whilst not fully accurate this will allow for the fluid velocity and swirl imparted to the flow by the propellers. In summary the investigation process will be as follows:

- 1) Geometry and Mesh Generation: The aircraft is designed to the specified parameters of the case and a valid mesh will be created to ensure that flow features are captured e.g. boundary layer.
- 2) RANS Simulation: Complete a RANS simulation of the configuration at the chosen conditions at a variety of AoAs.
- 3) Adaptation and Verification: With the completion of the RANS simulations the solutions will be inspected, and the mesh will be further refined if appropriate.
- 4) Geometry Generation for VLM: An identical geometry will need to be created with the fuselage, wing, strut, propeller sizing, and placement.
- 5) Complete VLM Simulations: Once the geometry of the aircraft for use within the VLM solver matches the RANS configuration.
- 6) Post-Processing: Gather the data from the simulation series, compare the target variables between RANS and VLM simulations. Finally detailing any differences between the two.

The results from this investigation will then be used to inform the modifications going forward. The goal being that once the configuration has been simulated, a change to the configuration will occur to either maximise or minimise chosen flow features to better understand the effect on the accuracy of the VLM solver when compared to RANS.

A. Vortex lattice method (VLM)

The steady vortex-lattice method (VLM) evaluates an aerodynamic surface as a lattice of horseshoe vortices, which extend out to infinity from the wing trailing edge, and whose strength is determined by solving a linear system of equations which result in a zero-normal-flow with respect to each panel. The strength of a given horseshoe vortex then directly leads to the pressure acting on its corresponding panel.

In this work, the well-established and verified open-source code VSPAERO is used, which has a range of features in addition to the basic VLM, such as: a panel discretisation that accounts for thickness effects; discretised and iterated wake filaments; zero-lift (parasite) drag estimation, etc. Its actuator disk implementation is also used, where a differential pressure leads to an axial velocity according to the conservation of momentum, and swirl is accounted for via the Conway method [8].

B. RANS-based simulations

Between the RANS-based Actuator-Surface and Actuator-Line simulations an identical solver setup is employed. For both cases, the open-source SU2 software suite is selected [9], solving the fully turbulent Navier-Stokes equations in Finite Volume form. Convective fluxes for the preliminary simulations make use of the second-order JST scheme with the time-averaged turbulent shear stresses provided via the one-equation Spalart-Almaras model. Modeling of the DHEP devices is performed via the use of an *Actuator-Disk* or *Actuator-Line* representation.

For meshing of the aircraft half-body configuration a multi-step strategy is used. Initially the open-source GMSH software [10] is used to generate the inviscid volume discretisation in addition to the semi-structured aircraft surface

mesh. To prepare the domain for viscous RANS simulation, a series of prism layers are inserted via an advancing normal strategy [11]. Following preliminary simulations on the initial mesh, solution-based volumetric mesh adaptation is performed to improve the overall topology of the domain and thus capture in higher fidelity the relevant flow features of interest.

Implementation of the actuator disk for RANS involves defining the propeller position, radius, advance ratio, and thrust/power coefficients per unit radius [12]. Propellers are modeled as internal boundary faces within the solver with the local force per unit cell area defined as:

$$F_a(\bar{r}) = \frac{2\rho_\infty V_\infty^2}{J^2 \pi \bar{r}} \left(\frac{dC_T}{d\bar{r}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where ρ_∞ is the freestream density; V_∞ is the freestream velocity; J is the advance ratio; C_T is the coefficient of thrust; and \bar{r} is the radial coordinate. $F_a(\bar{r})$ is the force per unit area, which is equivalent to the static pressure jump across the disk.

The force is decomposed into radial and tangential components and introduced as source terms superimposed to the diffusive flux on the cell faces. Swirl is accounted for via a momentum jump in the tangential direction.

IV. Initial Configuration Results

The following Table 4 shows the results from the RANS simulations of the aircraft described in Section III. A total of 5 AoAs were run between the chosen bounds and then the recorded lift and drag coefficients noted once the Cauchy lift and drag had sufficiently converged to a residual of 10^{-6} . A corresponding VSPAero VLM computation was completed for the same AoAs.

GA (W)-2				
AoA	RANS		VSPAero	
	C_L	C_D	C_L	C_D
-5	-0.2108	0.0357	-0.3848	0.0136
-2.5	0.1125	0.0227	-0.0382	0.0095
0	0.4742	0.0252	0.3090	0.0108
2.5	0.8253	0.0334	0.6551	0.0174
5	1.1203	0.0516	1.0008	0.0293

Table 4 Baseline RANS & VSPAero Results

With the results from both the RANS and VSPAero studies, a trend line can be created for both the lift and drag coefficients to see how these coefficients are predicted to behave as AoA changes.

(a) GA (W)-2 C_L v AoA

(b) GA (W)-2 C_D v AoA

Fig. 3 C_L and C_D Plots For the Baseline Configuration

Lift Variables	$\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha}$	C_{L0}	α_0
RANS	0.135	0.4643	-3.45
VSPAero	0.1386	0.3084	-2.23
Error	0.0036	0.1559	1.22

Table 5 Lift Variables and Absolute Error for Baseline Configuration

Drag Variables	$C_{D,Min}$	$\alpha_{C_{D,Min}}$	C_{D0}
RANS	0.0231	-1.063	0.024
VSPAero	0.0092	-2	0.0108
Error	0.0139	0.937	0.0132

Table 6 Drag Variables and Absolute Error for Baseline Configuration

To further inspect the behaviour of the flow, it was deemed necessary to create contours of supersonic flow over the aircraft. The figure below demonstrates, in red, regions of flow where Mach = 1.

(a) AoA = -5

(b) AoA = -2.5

(c) AoA = 0

(d) AoA = 2.5

(e) AoA = 5

Fig. 4 Baseline Aerofoil Contours of Mach = 1

Given the initiation of shock waves due to the presence of actuator disks in the $AoA = 2.5$ case, it was worthwhile to see if the influence of these regions were properly captured between the RANS and VSPAero simulations. The suction side C_p plots are demonstrated below.

(a) Suction Side Pressure Coefficient: RANS

(b) Suction Side Pressure Coefficient: VLM

Fig. 5 Comparison of Suction Side Pressure Coefficients, $AoA = 2.5$

V. Initial Configuration Discussion

The completion of the initial series of simulations with this configuration provides a clear illustration of the specific differences between the VLM and RANS approaches. Whilst there is a slight in the lift variables between the two techniques, the error in the drag-based variables are far more pronounced. Notably the error remains lowest at low $AoAs$ but significantly increases at an accelerating rate as the absolute AoA rises. Examining the Mach contours reveals supersonic regions at all $AoAs$, with these regions expanding as the absolute AoA increases. This progression aligns with the trend seen in the error, indicating that there may be a correlation between the growth of these regions and the error. Therefore, it becomes essential to investigate how a reduction in these regions will influence the overall error. One method to achieve this reduction involves altering the aircraft geometry that was outlined in Table 1. However, another effective strategy would be to change the aerofoil design. Currently, the aircraft employs the GA (W)-2, which has a high leading edge thickness. Selecting a thinner aerofoil can reduce the size of the shock regions without necessitating changes to the overall geometry. An appropriate alternative in this case would be the RAE 2822 aerofoil, a trans-sonic aerofoil with a thinner leading edge profile.

Fig. 6 GA (W)-2 and RAE2822 Aerofoils

This thinner aerofoil will aim to reduce the size of the shock regions on the wing, therefore showing if the supersonic regions have a significant impact on the error. With this modification made the same case was run for the 5 AoAs between -5° and 5° .

VI. Modified Aerofoil Results

After the completion of the RANS simulation campaign with the use of the RAE2822 aerofoil the following table of the recorded C_L and C_D at specific AoAs was created. Similar to in Table 4 these results are paired with corresponding VSPAero results.

RAE2822				
AoA	Rans		VSPAero	
	C_L	C_D	C_L	C_D
-5	-0.4283	0.0499	-0.6845	0.0218
-2.5	-0.1718	0.0280	-0.3368	0.0130
0	0.1714	0.0239	0.0124	0.0094
2.5	0.5241	0.0275	0.3606	0.0112
5	0.8418	0.0379	0.7089	0.0181

Table 7 RAE 2822 Aerofoil Results

As before these results were then plotted as two graphs of C_L vs Alpha and C_D vs Alpha. These were then used to build respective linear and quadratic trend lines so that the lift and drag key variables can be calculated.

(a) RAE2822 C_L v AoA

(b) RAE2822 C_D v AoA

Fig. 7 C_L and C_D Plots From the Modified Aerofoil

Lift Variables	$\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha}$	C_{L0}	α_0
RANS	0.1294	0.1875	-1.45
VSPAero	0.1394	0.0121	-0.09
Error	0.01	0.1754	1.36

Table 8 Lift Variables and Absolute Error for RAE2822 Aerofoil

Drag Variables	$C_{D,Min}$	$\alpha C_{D,Min}$	C_{D0}
RANS	0.0228	0.625	0.0231
VSPAero	0.0093	0.5	0.0094
Error	0.0135	0.125	0.0137

Table 9 Drag Variables and Absolute Error for RAE2822 Aerofoil

(a) AoA = -5

(b) AoA = -2.5

(c) AoA = 0

(d) AoA = 2.5

(e) AoA = 5

Fig. 8 Modified Aerofoil Contours of Mach = 1

Fig. 9 Comparison of Suction Side Pressure Coefficients, AoA = 2.5

VII. Modified Aerofoil Discussion

The results from the RAE 2822 aerofoil simulations suggest that the modification of the aerofoil has had the intended effect. As seen when comparing Figs. 4 and 8, the volume of the Mach contours has significantly decreased between identical angles of attack. Whilst it is still evident that the disks can cause the initiation of supersonic flow on the wing at the edges of the disk, especially with the 2.5° case, the region remains smaller than prior to the aerofoil change. However, as the strut aerofoil has not been modified, there are still significant shocks over the strut. This will have slightly skewed the aims of the study, but with a significant reduction of shocks on the wing there is an expectation that there will be a slight decrease in error for the important drag related variables. Table 9 supports this with a marked decrease in error with the $C_{D,Min}$; $\alpha C_{D,Min}$; and C_{D0} , between the newly calculated results and those gained from Table 6. However, whilst there has been a decrease in error regarding the drag variables, there has been a more significant increase in error for the lift variables. Whilst the trend of the lift curve generated from the VSPAero predictions being lower and with a sharper gradient has remained unchanged; the curve is both far lower and gradient far sharper than when compared to the previous case. This is illustrated by the higher error in C_{L0} and $\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha}$ as seen when comparing Table 5 and Table 8. This is likely caused by another of the variety of flow effects that VSPAero neglects as a VLM solver. This is further reinforced by the suction side pressure coefficient plots shown in Figure 9. Like in Figure 5, there not only is a lack of low pressure regions corresponding to the shocks created by the actuator disks, but also a higher suction side pressure coefficient in the VLM case when compared to both RANS cases. Demonstrating that this is an issue independent of the presence of shocks.

VIII. Conclusions

The objectives going forward were primarily focused on comparing the accuracy of a VLM approach when compared to high fidelity RANS simulations for a set LARW configuration with DHEP. Aiming to target potential sources of error and investigate the specific impact of said error source. By following a structured methodology, the study aimed to understand the effectiveness and limitations of VLM as a tool for conceptual aircraft design. For a meaningful comparison between RANS and VLM, the study concentrated on predicting key lift and drag variables between a baseline and modified configuration. With the base case utilising a GA (W)-2 aerofoil for the wing and a NACA 0024 foil for the strut, simulated under a feasible cruise environment. The investigation process involved several critical preliminary steps: designing and meshing the aircraft geometry, conducting RANS simulations, refining the mesh based on preliminary results, and performing VLM simulations with an identical geometry. The data from these studies were then analysed to compare predicted lift and drag variables, noting the errors in the baseline case. The initial simulations revealed that whilst VLM could predict lift variables with what could be considered a reasonable degree of accuracy; the drag based variables were significantly underestimated. This was most pronounced at the edges on the AoA domain. From the investigation of the Mach contours and the Cp plots of the baseline case from both the RANS and VLM approach, a secondary aerofoil; the RAE2822 was selected so that the core geometry of the aircraft would remain unchanged whilst also aiming to reduce the influence of supersonic flow on the results, noting that whilst the strut remains unchanged a decrease in the error of drag based variables would be expected to occur. Subsequent RANS simulations with the RAE 2822 aerofoil showed a reduction in supersonic regions and a corresponding decrease in drag-related errors, especially regarding the predicted minimum drag AoA. However, this modification also led to increased inaccuracies in lift predictions, indicating that other flow effects neglected by VLM still played a significant role. The results demonstrate that whilst modifications could work to improve certain aspects of VLM predictions, it also highlights the limitations of VLM in capturing complex aerodynamic features. In summary, the study provides valuable insights into the comparative performance of RANS and VLM simulations. Whilst VLM as a tool is increasingly attractive as a method to rapidly analyse the performance of aircraft concepts, the inherent limitations are challenging to consider when designing a specific aircraft configuration. With a consistent and considerable underestimation of lift and drag variables and attempts to design an aircraft configuration that aims to reduce said error not being fully successful, it is apparent that the use of higher fidelity methods such as RANS remains necessary for ensuring accuracy and reliability.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the scientific support of all the INDIGO partners. The authors acknowledge the financial support from the UKRI guaranteed fund for the Horizon Europe project INDIGO (Grant agreement 101096055, <https://indigo-sustainableaviation.eu>). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

References

- [1] Bradley, M. K., and Droney, C. K., "Subsonic Ultra Green Aircraft Research: Phase I final report," 2011. URL ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20110011321/downloads/20110011321.pdf.
- [2] Bradley, M. K., and Droney, C. K., "Subsonic Ultra Green Aircraft Research Phase II: N+4 Advanced Concept Development," 2012. URL ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20120009038.
- [3] de Vries, R., van Arnhem, N., Sinnige, T., Vos, R., and Veldhuis, L. L., "Aerodynamic interaction between propellers of a distributed-propulsion system in forward flight," *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2021.107009>.
- [4] Marcus, E. A., De Vries, R., Kulkarni, A. R., and Veldhuis, L. L., "Aerodynamic Investigation of an Over-the-Wing Propeller for Distributed Propulsion," *AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting*, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2018-2053>.
- [5] Borer, N. K., Patterson, M. D., Viken, J. K., Moore, M. D., Clarke, S., Redifer, M. E., Christie, R. J., Stoll, A. M., Dubois, A., and Bevirt, J., "Design and Performance of the NASA SCEPTOR Distributed Electric Propulsion Flight Demonstrator," *AIAA Aviation*, 2016. URL ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20160010157.
- [6] IV, J. F. G., Tetrault, P.-A., Gern, F. H., Nagshineh-Pour, A. H., Ko, A., Schetz, J. A., Mason, W. H., Kapania, R. K., Mason, W. H., Grossman, B., and Haftka, R. T., "Conceptual Design Studies of a Strut-Braced Wing Transonic Transport," *Journal of aircraft*, 2000. <https://doi.org/10.2514/2.2724>.
- [7] Xiong, J., Fugate, J., and Nguyen, N., "Investigation of Transonic Truss-Braced Wing Aircraft Transonic Wing-Strut Interference Effects using FUN3D," *AIAA Aviation Forum*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2019-3026>.
- [8] Sheridan, C. N. D., Pham, D. D. V., and Whiteside, S. K. S., "Evaluation of VSPAERO Analysis Capabilities for Conceptual Design of Aircraft with Propeller-Blown Wings," *AIAA Aviation*, 2021. URL ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20210017397/downloads/SheridanPham2021%200805.pdf.
- [9] Economon, T. D., Palacios, F., Copeland, S. R., Lukaczyk, T. W., and Alonso, J. J., "SU2: An Open-Source Suite for Multiphysics Simulation and Design," *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 54, No. 3, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.J053813>.
- [10] Geuzaine, C., and Remacle, J.-F., "Gmsh: A 3-D finite element mesh generator with built-in pre- and post-processing facilities," *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, Vol. 79, No. 11, 2009, pp. 1309–1331. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.2579>.
- [11] Alauzet, F., and Frazza, L., "Feature-based and goal-oriented anisotropic mesh adaptation for RANS applications in aeronautics and aerospace," *Journal of Computational Physics*, Vol. 439, 2021, p. 110340. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2021.110340>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0021999121002357>.
- [12] Saetta, E., Russo, L., and Tognaccini, R., "Implementation and validation of a new actuator disk model in SU2," *SU2 Conference*, 2020. URL su2foundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/SU2_paper_UniNa_withHeader-1.pdf.